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Effects of Print Media on Reading Habits in Social Studies Concepts among Secondary School Students in Kano State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study was on Effects of Print Media on Reading habits in Social Studies concepts among Secondary School Students in Kano State, Nigeria. Two objectives, two research questions and corresponding hypotheses guided the study. Quasi experimental research design specifically, pre test-post test, control group design was adopted. The population of the study consists of 11,281 (Male, 4,680 and Female,6,601) upper basic two students of 2022/2023 academic session in Kano State. A sample size of 276 (Male, 108 and Female,168) were selected from the target population using multistage sampling technique. An instrument titled Social Studies Reading Habit Test (SSRT) was developed and used for data collection. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer research questions, and t-test was used to test the two-null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that print media has significant effect on social studies students' reading habit and positively affects their performance. It was concluded that print media significantly improved students' reading habits in social studies. The study recommended that social studies teachers should employ different kind of print media to teach their students and students should be frequently engaged with reading tasks within and outside the classroom.

Keyword: Print media, Readership & Social Studies Students.

Introduction

Print media is one of the oldest and basic forms of mass communication. Teaching and learning can be conducted through print media. Print media includes textbooks, charts, pictures, graphics, bulleting, newspapers, magazines and journals. It plays a vital role in providing information and transfer knowledge (Diso & Haruna, 2020). Even after the advent of electronic media; the print media has not lost its charm or relevance. It has the advantage of making a longer impact on the minds of the reader, with more in-depth reporting and analysis. Print media such as books, journals, newspapers and magazines influence social, emotional and intellectual development of individuals. The most common medium encountered in school learning is still the books, which happens to be a channel used to send messages to the receiver (learners). Publications help individuals in research. Through illustrations and cartoons, people can find learning easier and more interesting (Maley, 2017).

Students may develop reading skills through the influence of print materials available for their study. Bala, (2017) is of the view that print media helps to enhance students' interest to read which broaden their perspectives towards global activities. Thus, reading newspaper and magazines not only teach social studies better but give current knowledge of the world happenings. Furthermore, if at higher secondary level, there is an adequate and appropriate use of print media, learners familiarize themselves with the world surrounding them (Mujittaba, 2022). When a piece of news is presented in the newspaper and magazines this will enhance students' knowledge. The task accompanying each text from the print media used in social studies classrooms would give the learners adequate confidence to read and view news items in social studies through print media outside the classroom. Print media is a tool that we use to pass information from sender to the receiver in this case, this research intends to assess the influence of print media in reading habits among social studies students in secondary school. This is to say that print media influence the interest of social studies students to engage or develop readership habit. Therefore, reading is the foundation of all formal and informal learning. Future success is dependent on the learners' reading ability. It is the gateway to success and the number of time students spends in reading is the indicator of successful academic life in future (Wigfield, Guthrie, Perencevich & Taboada, 2008).

Authors publish audio format of their manuscript and textbooks to assist students in Upper basic schools but even this also become ineffective. Students with a poor reading habit in Upper basic schools face a lot of challenges if they make it to the tertiary institution, mostly because they are compelled to read huge volumes of academic books. They may find it even more challenging because they required to do their research at the library or online to fully understand and succeed in their course work. The extent to which secondary school' students neglect the value attached to print media is what motivate the researcher to assess the effect of print media on reading habits of social studies students in Upper basic schools in Kano State.

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This is with the view of facilitating healthy discourse amongst stakeholders in education on how to reverse and enforce readership and interest in social studies students.

Print media are very essential in teaching and learning situation, especially in secondary and tertiary levels of education, as it stands as an instrument in which knowledge and information are directed to the learner. Considering the fact that, in most cases, the mode of assessment (examinations) in Nigerian Upper basic schools mostly is based on written form. Students in this regard, have to read notes and textbooks in order to confront any examination. Apart from that, teaching and learning social studies requires the use of print media such as textbooks, magazines, charts and journals among others. The use of different types of print media is inevitable due to the broadening nature of the social studies curriculum.

As multi-disciplinary subject, social studies depend heavily on the content of social sciences and humanities to realize its objectives of preparing people to become good and effective citizens in a democratic society with links to other societies, social studies incorporate the personal and social experiences of students and their cultural heritage. It links factors outside the individual, particularly the development and use of reflective thinking, problem-solving, rational decision-making skills, to create involvement in social action. Therefore, social studies have been defined by different scholars based on their point of viewed. Ikumelu, (2012) in Godebe, (2016) perceived social studies as a program of study that focuses on man, his environments and the interrelationship between man and his environments. In other words, social studies have three dimensions, first, the study of man; second, the study of man's environments (social, economic, physical, cultural); and third, the study of how man affects his various environments, and how these environments affect man. There is reciprocal relationship between man and his environment as social studies explored it to the students how to handle their environmental issues. The definition explained the three dimensions of social studies in which are all vested on man's both physical and social environment.

Social studies in Nigeria has to do with the development of socio-civic and personal behavior. Considering this, Nigerian policy recognizes the importance of social studies, making it a core subject in Nigerian primary and upper basic schools and assigns it the responsibility to develop the essential knowledge, values, and skills associated with citizenship. Therefore, social studies at all levels of the education system are tailored towards the realization of Nigerian educational goals. Print media is a revolutionary evolution that has buried the gap of communication with the aid of tangible printed assets such as books, newspapers, magazines, letters. among various targeted groups of people so that the hierarchy of information would never get broken down due to slacking conversation. Print media has several sources to destine its significant role among which newspapers and magazines are the gigantic dominants for intermediating information till the date today while business letters, brochures, billboards, pamphlets, signboards, postcards and advertisements play a secondary role in catapulting a large audience in one go (Okeeffe, 2012).

Print Media in education is a worldwide programme whereby all types of print media are used to promote education in school classrooms. Print media such as books, journals, newspapers and magazines influence social, emotional and intellectual development of individuals. The most common medium encountered in school learning is still the book, which happens to be a channel used to send messages to the receiver. Publications help individuals in research. Print media provide a rich learning experience in the classroom. Media in the classroom engage students in learning and provide a richer experience (Bala 2016).

Printed media help a lot in transmitting the culture and history of the society without a writing text many facts regarding to world history would have been missed. Knowledge can be a permanent on students' mind if they can open books to read and illustrated the information written on it. In Nigerian classes, textbook is the most commonly used to deliver information. In each curriculum there is available textbooks that will guide both teachers and students in getting the information and the successful implementation.

A textbook is a type of print media that is transmitting information to all students. Print media can help the intellectual and professional person to transmission their knowledge and experience to readers. Newspapers have provided the practice section for primary and secondary school students to do their assignments more especially social studies students that deal with global phenomena. Print media such as newspaper and magazines have a contributing factor to the development of reading habits. As they serve as a channel through which messages, information, ideas, and knowledge are disseminated more easily. Reading is one of the major skills in present-day literary society. Books are the storehouse of knowledge and this knowledge is usually translated through reading. Reading involves the ability to identify ink marking on paper by way of formal elements of the language i.e. identifying these inks marking either as alphabets or words and then knowing the meaning of the words so identified (Olanrewaju, 2016). People read to be able to interpret information into meaning. The extraction of meaning from a

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written piece of work either of a line, paragraph or more is referred to as comprehension. Students can generate the information only when they read and understand the instruction delivered to them is either from the classroom or outside the classroom.

Reading is defined as a cognitive process that involves decoding symbols to arrive at meaning. Reading is an active process of constructing meanings of words. Reading with a purpose helps the reader to direct information towards a goal and focuses their attention. Although the reasons for reading may vary, the primary purpose of reading is to understand the text. Reading is a thinking process. It allows the reader to use what he or she have already known, also called prior knowledge. During this processing of information, the reader uses strategies to understand what they are reading, uses themes to organize ideas, and uses textual clues to find the meanings of new words (Gabriel 2008). Reading is an essential tool for knowledge transfer and the habit of reading is an academic activity that increases skills in reading strategies. To know about the world and its environment, a child helps himself through reading books, newspapers and other magazines. Once the child has been taught to read and has developed a love for books, he can explore for himself the wealth of human experiences and knowledge through reading. Children, who miss the opportunity of getting in touch with books in their early stages of life, find it hard to acquire good reading habits in their later years (Hassan, 2010). Teachers and students tap information through a reading which came in a different form of print media. It also one of the basic skills which children learnt from school how to read and understand the message that came to them in a text mode.

Different research works have been conducted on reading and print media, some of these studies were conducted outside the country, but majority that were reviewed by the researcher have been found conducted in Nigeria. Among are those conducted and reviewed by the researcher are; Jude and Udosen, (2012) conducted a study on the influence of print media strategies (magazines and Novels) in determining the development of students' reading competence in AkwaIbom State, Nigeria. Abdulrasheed, Abdulkarim, Dogara, and Umar, (2015) conducted a research titled "An assessment of reading habit among Upper basic schools in Kaduna metropolis. Njeze (2013), conducted a research on use of Newspapers and Magazines in the academic pursuits of university students: Case Study of Covenant University. This present study examined the Effects of Print Media on Reading Habits in Social Studies Concepts among Secondary School Students in Kano State, Nigeria

Statement of the Research Problem

Despite the value and importance attached to print media in teaching and learning, students nowadays neglect to take its advantage and embrace it as a reliable tool of sourcing information, rather they use various electronic media to watch motion pictures or listen to audio (Mujittaba 2022). What becomes an order of the day is that students turn their attention to books when their examination is around the corner without consulting print media even during their leisure time.

The researcher observed that the unavailability of print media in Upper basic schools and the poor functioning of school libraries are among the root causes of poor reading habits among social studies students in Upper basic schools. Many students come to school regularly but most of them have no textbooks. Even teachers do not encourage and motivate students in any form of reading activities. Also, inappropriate teaching methods by the teachers might be the contributing factor for the students to develop an undesirable habit in reading. Students are poorly motivated to read. Apart from the teacher's failure to motivate students to read, the parent does not find it worthy to equip their children with reading materials.

The emergence of availability of electronic media further contributes immensely in fading away from the value of print media in the eyes of both students and parent (Mujittaba, 2022). Some students using their smart phones to browse, and chat with their friends, sometimes they watch movies and play music. This poor attitude serves as problems that make it difficult when it comes to reading. It has been itching deeply into the mind of many Nigerians that, lack of interest to read and poor reading habits among students of Upper basic schools is attributed to poor performance in their examinations. Many parents and teachers complain about students of our generation who have not developed reading habits among themselves. Officials of the West African Examinations Council (WAEC) and teachers of English complain of the kind of written English by today's generation of students (Olowolagba, 2018). The net result is the poor performance of many students in final examinations. One of the many issues confronting students nowadays is perhaps, not their inability to read but their lack of interest.

As a result of this poor reading habit, they failed woefully in their examinations. This leads to poor grades for students and difficulty in trying to find or advance to a good job in adulthood. Given the above, the researcher finds it interested to investigate the influence of print media on reading habits among social studies students in upper basic school in Kano State.

Objectives of the study

The following specific objectives guided the study:

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1. Determine reading habits mean performance score in social studies concepts among upper basic class two students taught using print media and those expose to lecture teaching method in Kano State.
2. Determine reading habits mean performance score in social studies concepts among upper basic class two students taught using textbooks and those expose to lecture teaching method in Kano State.

Research Questions:

1. What is the reading habits mean performance score in social studies concepts among upper basic class two students taught using print media and those expose to lecture teaching method in Kano State?
2. What is the reading habits mean performance score in social studies concepts among upper basic class two students taught using Textbook and those expose to lecture teaching method in Kano State?

Hypotheses:

1. There is no significant difference between the reading habits mean performance score in social studies concepts among upper basic class two students taught using print media and those expose to lecture teaching method in Kano State.
2. There is no significant difference between the reading habits mean performance score in social studies concepts among upper basic class two students taught using Textbooks and those expose to lecture teaching method in Kano State.

Methodology

The study adopted Quasi experimental design to assess the Effects of Print Media on Reading Habits in Social Studies Concepts Among Secondary School Students in Kano State, Nigeria. The design pretest- posttest, Experiment- Control group method requires that pretest be administered on students, after which treatment be giving to the experimental group. While the control group receive no treatment. And thereafter both the Experimental and Control groups receive post-test.

The population comprises of eleven thousand two hundred and eighty-one (11,281) upper basic 2 students (male 4,680 and female 6,601) of 2022/2023 academic session. Therefore, the population of this study are located in twenty-five (25) public Upper Basic 2 School students in Dala Education zone which covers Dala and Gwale Local Government Councils of Kano State, Nigeria. For the purpose of this study, four intact classes from four schools comprise 276 (Male 108 and Female 168) students who were sampled using multistage sampling techniques.

The instrument for data collection was Social Studies Reading Habit Test (SSRT) which was developed by researcher. The SSRT consist of six short passages in social studies topics for the purpose of the treatment. The topics are family system, our culture, marriage system, transportation, national economy and social and health issues. At the end of each passage five items were drawn to make a total of 30 items. The instruments were subjected to construct and content validity. A pilot study aimed to determine the reliability coefficient of the designed instrument. Therefore, the researcher conducted a pilot study at one Secondary School from Dala Education zone which is Government Junior Secondary School Masaka. The school is part of the population, but not in the sample size. Thirty questionnaires were distributed for conducting the pilot testing. The reliability of the research instruments was determined by the outcome of the pilot study. After the pilot study, the data collected from the Pilot study was statistically analyzed for reliability index using Spearman-Brown (r) for measuring reading habit, the result obtained was 0.770. This result showed that the instrument was reliable for the study at hand.

The data collected on the effects of print media on reading habits in Social Studies concepts among secondary school students in Kano State, Nigeria was analyzed using statistical tools. Both descriptive and inferential statistical tools were used in the analysis of the data. At descriptive level, the researcher used mean and standard deviation to analyze responses of the research questions, while at inferential level, the researcher tested the hypotheses using inferential statistics of independent sample t-test to test the two hypotheses.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the reading habits mean performance score in social studies concepts among upper basic class two students taught using print media and those expose to lecture teaching method in Kano State?

Table 1: Description of Post-test Performance of Students Taught Social Studies Using Print Media and those exposed to lecture method.

Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Difference
Experimental	151	61.56	15.68	17.64

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Control	125	43.92	11.14
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Source: Field work 2023

Table 1 reveals the post-test performance of students taught social studies, in Upper basic schools using print media and those exposed to lecture method in Kano State. The mean scores as presented above shows that students taught Social Studies using print media at post-test (61.56) performed better as against those who were exposed to lecture method performance of (43.92), which yielded a mean difference of 17.64. Yet, the corresponding standard deviation of 15.68 and 11.14 were obtained respectively. This implies that students performed better if they were taught social studies with different kind of print media.

Research Question 2:

What is the reading habits mean performance score in social studies concepts among upper basic class two students taught using Textbook and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Kano State?

Table 2: Computation of Mean and Standard Deviation of Students' performance of Experimental and Control Groups

Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Difference
Experimental	151	61.55	15.68	
Control	125	53.88	12.75	7.67

Source: Field work, 2023

Table 2 revealed the post-test students' performance of both control and experimental group taught social studies, in Upper basic schools using printed short passages. The mean scores as presented above shows that students taught social studies concepts using printed short passages at post-test (61.56) performed better as their performance exceeds the control group performance of (53.88), with corresponding standard deviation of 15.58 and 12.75 respectively which yielded a mean difference of 7.67. This implies that students' performance at post-test using short passages varied widely from that of control group who received no treatment.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between the reading habits mean performance score in social studies concepts among upper basic class two students taught using print media and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Kano State.

Table 3: Paired t-test showing differences in post-test scores of students taught some Social Studies concepts using print media and those taught using lecture method in Upper basic II in Kano State.

Groups	N	M	SD	t cal.	Df	α	P- value	Decision
Experimental	151	61.56	15.68					
Control	151	43.92	11.14	150	10.98	0.05	0.01	Rejected

Source: Field work, 2023

Table 3 reveals the post-test performance of students taught social studies, using print media and those taught using lecture method. The Table shows that there is significant effect on print media on student's reading habit comparing their performance with control group in post-test. The control group mean score is (43.92) against the experimental group mean score of (61.56), with standard deviation of 15.68 and 11.14 respectively. The t-test calculated of 10.98 is less than the p-value 0.01 ($p < 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated there is no significant difference between the reading habits mean performance score in social studies concepts among upper basic class two students taught using print media and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Kano State was rejected.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between the reading habits mean performance score in social studies concepts among upper basic class two students taught using Textbooks and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Kano State

Table 4: Independent sample t-test showing differences in post-test scores of students taught some social studies concepts using short passages for experimental group and control group without any treatment in secondary school in Kano State.

Groups	N	M	SD	t. cal.	Df	α	P- value	Decision
Experimental	151	61.55	15.68					
Control	125	53.89	12.75	4.39	274	0.05	0.00	Rejected

Source: Field work, 2023

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Table 4 reveals the performance of Students taught using short passages for experimental group and control group that received no treatment. The table shows that there is significant difference between the performance of experimental and control groups. After administering the post-test experimental group performance is higher than the control group performance with the mean score of (61.55) against the mean score of control group (53.89) with standard deviation of 15.68 and 12.75 respectively. The t-test calculated was 4.39 which is less than the p-value 0.01 ($p < 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference in post-test performance of students taught Social Studies using printed short passages and those without printed short passages in Upper basic schools in Kano State was rejected.

Discussion of Findings

This section discussed the findings of the study, alongside the findings of other researchers. Firstly, finding number one reveals that there is significance deference between experimental group who taught social studies concept using different kind print media and control group who were expose with lecture method. This can be deduced from the results of both descriptive and inferential analysis. For instance, the descriptive analysis revealed that the mean score of control group is 43.92, while the experimental group mean scores is reading 61.56. For inferential analysis the result indicated that the calculated P-value of (0.01) is less than the critical value of (0.05) therefore the null hypothesis is rejected. This finding is in agreement with the findings of Jude and Udosen, (2012) in their study on the influence of print media strategies (magazines and Novels) in determining the development of students' reading competence in Akwalbom State, Nigeria, Jude and Udosen (2012), established that when students are exposed to print media, their higher reading competencies is developed and their performance would rise much higher.

The second finding revealed that experimental group who were taught some topics in social studies using short passages performed better against. Thus, the descriptive analysis revealed that the mean scores of experimental groups after post-test was 61.56 with standard deviation of 15.58 was quite different with those of control group that taught without short passages with mean scores of 53.88 with standard deviation of 12.75 which yielded the margin of 7.67. This implies that students' performance at post-test using short passages for the experimental group varied from that of the control group which received no treatment because there is a wide gap between the performance of experimental and that control groups. Equally, the inferential analysis revealed that the calculated P-value of (0.00) is less than the critical value (0.05) therefore the null hypothesis was rejected. This finding established that, there was a significant difference in their performance. This finding is in contrary to that of Gulzar (2014), in his study effects of print media: A study of reading skills among University EFL Students. Gulzar (2014), revealed that a fixed and limited reading material of prescribed textbooks is one of the main causes of students' limitations of reading competence. Also, students were not exposed to the English language apart from the textbook materials in the classrooms at large and reading activities were also limited for the proper exposure to the reading skills. In view of this finding teachers should be encourages to make good use of textbook in the process of teaching. The use of textbook brings positive difference in students' performance.

Conclusion

Print Media significantly improved students' performance in Social Studies and facilitated their reading habits.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made:

1. Social studies teachers should be encouraged to be using different kinds of print media in teaching social studies. This enables the students' performance to be improved and their readership attitudes will be developed. This can be done by the school Quality Assurance Officer and at workshops.
2. Students should be frequently engaged with reading tasks within and outside the classroom. This is in line with developing students' reading interests and good reading habits so that their academic performance can be improved to a significant level.

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